

REGULATION OF COMMON PROCESSES BETWEEN SUPPLY AND LOGISTICS IN THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY

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The current stage of development of market relations in Uzbekistan requires serious decisions from local enterprises to increase the efficiency of their activities. Of particular interest to practical economists is the assessment of the efficiency of production activities, the cost of economic resources, as well as the introduction of accurate information technologies and ensuring the innovative functioning of enterprises. Most companies themselves prefer innovation in production. Despite all efforts to achieve the goal, in rare cases an enterprise can profit from successful innovations according to the standards of specialists.

Problems have a common cause: inefficient management, that is, improper optimization of business processes in the enterprise.

One of the main conditions for ensuring the competitiveness of Uzbek goods on the world market remains the improvement of cheap, fast and safe transport logistics.

From this it can be learned that from early economic theories, an indirect conclusion can be drawn about the need for a transport and logistics system as the main condition for the development of trade between peoples.

At the same time, figures in the field of transport logistics in the world show that the potential of this branch of the global economy is quite significant.

In particular, by 2020, the share of transport services in the gross domestic product (GDP) of the world's countries will range from 8 to 12 percent, and the value of the global logistics industry will amount to 9.6 trillion dollars. And the cost of cargo delivery services at the international level is 4.1 trillion US dollars. The US dollar.

In addition, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan has put forward numerous initiatives to consolidate the National Transport System in the international arena.

An enterprise is a complex system and therefore can be represented as a single system of fields of activity. Therefore, management should be carried out relatively fully, in all areas such as production, personnel, product sales and finance. In unstable conditions, various models of control systems are being formed. At the level of an individual enterprise, innovative development implies the introduction of useful innovations that contribute to the competitiveness of the enterprise in the market. Optimization of the company's activities is possible only with a comprehensive analysis of existing business processes. In this case, the analysis shows what actions need to be taken to increase the optimality of the relationships and interactions built at the enterprise and the effectiveness of activities. Building an effective business process scheme will be beneficial to the enterprise, as it will create opportunities for formalization of activities, as well as create a basis for work in case of any changes in the business.

Business processes allow you to quickly optimize the company's activities without bringing it to a critical point. This is the only way management can influence the usual business strategy and quickly change it.

With the help of competent modeling, it is possible to optimize the work of an enterprise, predict and minimize the risks that arise at each stage of its activity. The organization of business process modeling allows you to evaluate each process individually and the costs as a whole. Modeling of business processes of an enterprise concerns a number of aspects of its work. In the process of modeling, the organizational structure changes; the functions of specialists and departments are optimized; the rights and responsibilities of management are redistributed; internal regulatory documents and operation technologies are changed; there are new requirements for the automation of business processes, etc. Business process modeling defines the main goal, which is to systematize information about the enterprise and its activities in a visual graphic image. Thanks to this approach, it is much more convenient for an enterprise to process data. When modeling business processes, it is necessary to reflect the structure of actions in the organization, the features and details of their implementation, as well as the chronology of the workflow.

Their analysis plays an important role in optimizing business processes. Before starting to improve business processes, it is necessary to analyze each step. After the analysis, ideas appear for further optimization of a particular process. There are the following stages of business process optimization.

1. Identification of inefficient processes.
2. Mapping the process.

3. Business process analysis.
4. Search for optimal solutions.
5. Optimize the process through restructuring, automation, or the use of technology that completely changes its operation.

The need to optimize business processes depends on the level of competition in the industry. For example, manufacturing priorities focus on supply chain programs and customer needs for self-service and data access. When optimizing business processes in an enterprise of any industry, goals, methods and techniques for managing these processes, their volumes and limits are determined. It is also necessary to allocate the necessary resources to identify the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of the existing process. After that, a schedule is developed according to which business processes are optimized.

The topic of optimizing logistics departments is more relevant today than ever, especially in connection with the possibility of increasing the efficiency of various product transportation systems through planning. The TDL Textile enterprise is developing very rapidly and is actively increasing its production capacity, its structure and organization allow us to achieve our goals and objectives today. The main activity of the enterprise is the production of cotton fabrics (OKVED code 13.20.2). Optimization of business processes is necessary to increase production capacity and increase production efficiency.

The methodology of logistics requires, after studying the relationship of an object with the external environment, to proceed to the analysis of its structure. Acting as an element of the "national economy" system, the region currently represents a complex system consisting of various subsystems, which indicates that the region is characterized by the first feature of the system - integrity and segmentation. The allocation of subsystems of the region can be carried out from different positions and criteria. At the same time, taking into account the logistic methodology of the study, it is necessary to use the method of transition from the general to the particular, according to which the region is first divided into the largest subsystems, and then each of them is studied separately and in combination with other elements.

Changing the traditional content of market demand and market supply in a more complex global economic system affects the strategic goals of participants in the logistics chain: stimulating demand and minimizing total costs, improving the quality parameters of the entire system, increasing environmental, resource-saving, and social potential.

The dynamically changing market environment and increased competition require rapid coordination of processes beyond the boundaries of one business entity. The application of the logistics supply chain management concept supports joint business activities and ensures inter-organizational, functional, organizational coordination, synchronization and control.

Logistics is the methodology of the process of organizational and analytical optimization of complex economic systems and subsystems. The competitiveness of an economic entity that unites all components of its activities (innovation, organizational, supply, production, distribution and marketing) has the ability to effectively solve emerging problems and ensure sustainable development. In these conditions, the crucial task is to coordinate and optimize end-to-end flow processes in enterprise management, which significantly changes the criteria for evaluating efficiency: the logistics approach does not take into account overhead costs, the criterion of the minimum amount of costs is used, based on the optimal value of each condition in the logistics system.

Interaction with logistics of such disciplines as management, marketing and trade is an economic component of trade, production and commercial activities in entrepreneurship, these are "logistics management", "marketing logistics", "commercial logistics". In a consumer-oriented economy, the functional separation of logistics, management, marketing and commerce is unacceptable.

Functional logistics management at the enterprise determines the achievement of the enterprise's goal by special logistics functions (supply quality management, risk management, logistics cost management, logistics innovation management) with general logistics functions (organization, planning, regulation, coordination, control, accounting and analysis). The peculiarity of logistics management is that it is connected by infrastructure with all functional areas of management (investment, innovation, production, financial, information, personnel) for strategic and tactical goals and objectives, as well as for managing the procurement of material resources, production processes and sales of finished products. In this regard, the management of the management system as a whole should be considered in the unity of three aspects:

- as a process of interrelated functions;
- as a set of tools and methods aimed at achieving the goals of the enterprise in accordance with the internal capabilities and business conditions;
- as a means of regulating (and regulating) employee relationships with colleagues, business partners and consumers.

The functional directions of production, sales and logistics at the enterprise add a certain profit to material resources and form for the consumer the total profit of the finished product (service), which is characterized by the following components:

- the usefulness of the form (creation in the process of converting the material flow into the required finished product);
- the usefulness of place and the usefulness of time (created by the delivery (transportation, movement) of economic flows that meet the needs (for timely replenishment of stocks, information, maintenance);
- utility of ownership (created as a result of attracting consumers to the product, generating demand and stimulating the desire to purchase the product).

In this regard, as a set of material labor, a "complete value chain" is formed, the result of which is "total (aggregate) utility".

Conclusion

It is assumed that when using an integrated logistics management system and analyzing the full cost of business processes, the end result is always to determine the most economical option to meet the needs of the buyer. However, costs can change in all parts of the supply chain, which means that the costs of performing certain business processes can increase. This is possible if such a step leads to greater savings on related business processes and, ultimately, to a reduction in their full cost at a constant level of customer satisfaction.

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